

ABOUT THE SPIRITUAL ARTISTIC WORKS OF ABDULLA AWLANI
О ДУХОВНОМ И ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОМ ТВОРЧЕСТВЕ
АБДУЛЛЫ АВЛАНИ

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Annotation: The role and importance of pedagogical scientific heritage of Abdulla Avloni, one of the exponents of the Enlightenment movement, in pedagogical moral education in the process of organizing the educational system is highlighted in the article. Abdulla Awlani's views on many works on education and their influence on the education of the young generation in the current era of globalization were studied.

Key words: Jadid, lesson, competence, result, education, Abdulla Avloni, the work "Turkish Gulistan or Morality", "Adibi Sany", stories for knowledge and enlightenment, "Hajjoj ila dervish", "The miser's garden does not grow",

One of the famous representatives of the Uzbek national culture of the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century, an enlightened poet, playwright, journalist, scientist, state and public figure, Abdulla Avloni introduced innovations in the method of reading and teaching and established new schools. . He left an indelible mark in the history of the Uzbek nation by carrying out important educational activities such as imparting modern knowledge to students, teaching Eastern and Western languages. He was the "father" of Uzbek pedagogy and one of the first in our country to receive the title of professor. Studying the legacy of Abdulla Avloni is one of the current issues. On October 8, 2020, the Head of our State signed the Decree "On further study of the legacy of repression victims and additional measures to perpetuate their memory". The following words of the order are relevant: "State and public figures who were brutally repressed by the authoritarian regime in today's era, when global threats are increasing in the world and the realization of national identity and the recovery of our true history are more important than ever, It remains an urgent task to perpetuate the names and memories of the representatives of science, culture and art, literature, and thousands of our compatriots who have ordinary professions, and to educate our young generation in the spirit of love and loyalty to our Motherland and people, following the example of their courage and fortitude.

Abdulla Avloni's pedagogical views are of great importance in the creation of the Uzbek national school today. Interest in the in-depth study of Avloni's creative heritage is growing. Avloni divides human behavior into good and bad behavior based on the views of the "scholar of ethics". He describes 31 virtues in "Good manners" and 20 vices in "Bad manners". To prove his opinions, he cites verses of the Qur'an and hadiths, as well as the opinions of famous thinkers such as Aristotle, Socrates, Ibn Sina, Sa'di, Mirza Bedil. After expressing his attitude to each moral category, he attached a couplet or a proverb expressing the content of that opinion. In dividing people's behavior into good and bad behavior, it is based on their self-education. He includes virtues such as fortitude, tenderness, courage, discipline, conscience, love for the motherland among good qualities, and considers vices such as anger, lust, ignorance, stupidity as signs of bad character. Avloni's early poems singing the ideas of enlightenment and national renaissance will always remain a priceless property of Uzbek national renaissance literature. In his poems belonging to this series, he enriched the poetic forms of Uzbek classical literature with great social content, enlightening ideas, comic spirit and folk melodies. Abdulla Avloni also wrote a number of poems and parables for children. In these works, the poet aims to expand the scope of thinking of school-aged children, to instill in them love for school and books, work, nature, and the Motherland. Many of his poems are based on the idea of loving the Motherland. In these poems, the poet described the Motherland in simple and sincere verses, which not only those of the middle of the 10s, but also today's school-age children can get great aesthetic pleasure from them. In fact, the poet begins the description of the Motherland, "Mines are extracted from its mountains, grains are extracted from its lands... It is a very pleasant air, It is rocky and sandy with deserts, It is not Tashkent, it is melting stone, Its cuts are melting flower", - children say to the motherland. achieves great affection. It is known that the perfection of a person is determined not by his external appearance, but by his spiritual world. The development and future of the society depends on the spiritual maturity of the people living in this society.

After all, it is a fact of life that a society with a bright future cannot be built with spiritually poor people. The task of educating a perfect person is entrusted to the school to a certain extent. Therefore, the perfection of our children, who are the owners of tomorrow, is related to this place of knowledge. Therefore, we should focus all our attention on the educational work carried out in the school. This mainly depends on the educator-coach and the effectiveness of the educational work he is doing. In order to establish kindness and real human relations between people, the educational hours of the class and the lessons of moral education are of great importance. After all, good education is an invaluable asset of a person.

Raising the young generation into mature people through education is one of the most pressing issues facing us. In particular, loyalty to one's homeland, one's nation - one's people, sacrifice, tolerance, justice, humility, kindness, self-awareness, love, loyalty, thirst for knowledge, striving for excellence, hard work, tolerance, patience Contentment, generosity, courage, awareness, struggle against various evils, concern, hospitality, honoring friendship and brotherhood, unlimited respect for our ancestors, carefully preserving our nation, language and values are the characteristics of our nation.

In 1913, A. Avloni's work "Turkish Gulistan or Morality" was published, which included the following features. In this work, Abdulla Avloni pays special attention to the development of children's thinking in education. Because acquiring the ability to think means striving towards noble ideas. Therefore, it is difficult for a smart person to be immoral. Avloni sees these two concepts as close and united. Abdulla Avloni, like the mature intellectuals of his time, is very concerned about the development of the national language. Adib: "Language and literature are the mirror of life of every nation that shows its presence in the world. To lose the national language is to lose the spirit of the nation," he says. He also assesses the position of the word as defining human dignity from a universal point of view. He

expresses his thoughts about language and speech etiquette as follows: "Words are scales that measure a person's level and perfection, knowledge and virtue. Those with intelligence know a person's thoughts and intentions, knowledge and strength, value and value from his words." Alloma assesses honesty and truthfulness as one of the most important human qualities of a person and says in this regard: "Truthfulness means truthfulness in deeds and truthfulness in words. A person grows a garden to health and a flower garden to happiness through the path of truth. Truth is the mother of the best qualities, such as compassion, righteousness, and justice, which is the root of humanity."

This work of Abdulla Avloni was published in 1913 in Tashkent in the Ilin printing house in the lithographic (lithographic) method. The work was published for the second time in 1917, taking into account the need for such a textbook. Both editions do not differ in size. Only the first is the signature of the secretary Abdusalam Abdurahman's son, and the second is the signature of the secretary Abdul Mannon ibn Abdul Majid (the famous actor of the Uzbek National Theater Mannon Uyghur Majidov). The third edition of "Turkish Gulistan or Morality" was published in 1967 by the "Teacher" publishing house. In this case, the religious phrases found in the work, the wisdom from the Hadith, were omitted according to the requirements of the time. The work was published by the publishing house "Teacher" in 1992 in the original copy (in the Uzbek script based on the Arabic script) and with the text converted to the Uzbek script based on the Russian alphabet, as well as a dictionary of difficult words. . The fifth edition of "Turkish Gulistan or Morality" is the most perfect among the previous editions. In this, a facsimile of the text of the Uyghur autograph of the secretary Mannon, the text converted into the new Uzbek script based on the Latin script, and a dictionary of difficult words are given. In addition, selected stories and poems from Abdulla Avloni's works "First Teacher", "Second Teacher", "School Gulistani" were also attached.

In conclusion, we can say that Abdulla Awlani considers the acquisition of knowledge as the highest quality of a person. He said that science is dead if it does not serve the benefit of society, if science is not used for the welfare of the people. That's why the writer suggests to the people to engage in the arts that are more useful. Abdulla Avloni, as a famous pedagogue and coach, devoted his whole life to the development of enlightenment. In his scientific works and textbooks, he expressed his thoughts about the Motherland, patriotism, science, ethics, enlightenment, human perfection, and the development of society [8]. The thinker Allama considered it truly noble to encourage people to do good, to live with the desire to be good towards all people in the world. All his pedagogical thoughts and teachings made an important contribution to the development of the history of national pedagogy. The noble ideas put forward by Adib in terms of education, manners and manners are still relevant today and serve the development of modern Uzbek pedagogy.

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